

**PROBLEMS OF STUDENT TEACHERS STUDYING IN
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION IN SALEM DISTRICT,
TAMIL NADU**

G. Rajasekaran* & Dr. G. Pazhanivelu**

* Ph.D Scholar, Department of Education, Tamil University,
Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor, Department of Tamil Studies in Foreign Countries,
Tamil University, Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Vaibhavi Nandagiri & Leena Philip, "Impact of Influencers from Instagram and YouTube on their Followers", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 4, Issue 1, Page Number 66-70, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, R&D Modern Research Publication, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The present study focuses at investigating the impact of Problems of Student Teacher Studying in College of Education in Salem District, Tamilnadu. A sample of 692 student teachers studying in various college of education in Salem District and using random sampling technique. For attaining this, the researcher adopted normative survey method. The data were analyzed using percentage analysis and differential analysis. Results, It is found that female were better than male Student teachers in Colleges of Education. The present study reveals that Rural Student Teachers have more problems than Urban Student Teachers of Colleges of Education.

Key Words: Problems, Student Teachers & College of Education

Introduction:

Teacher Education must comprise of features to enable student Teachers to understand the way learning occurs and create possible solutions conducive to learning. They should learn to view knowledge as personal experienced constructed and shared in the pedagogical contexts rather than combated in the external reality of text books. The self study has to be promoted among the students, and learner controlled self-learning strategies should supplement the conventional methods of classroom instructions.

Practical application of computers for education and computer assisted instruction are popularized among the students. Information and communication technology (ICT) is also being applied in most of the Teacher learning courses, and also encouraging audio visual aids are major requests of the B. Ed programme. Most of the training institutions have the multimedia laboratory for information and educational Technology. Students are also encouraged to undertake case studies of school children and school and community surveys. Professional development of Teachers begins with the acquisition of competencies. In most of the Training Institutes conducted language proficiency courses consisting of structured grammar, discussion, debates, film viewing, translation, vocabulary building, chat sessions, brain storming, news reporting and dramatics, vocational training is an integral component of this B. Ed programme. Teacher Educational Institutes for quality improvement conduct many state levels, National level and international level seminars and student Teachers enjoy the chance of participating and presenting papers.

Review of Related Literature:

Bhargava, S.C. (2001) made a study on comparison of cognitive classroom verbal interaction of prospective science Teachers of two years B.Ed. course teaching physical and biological component of secondary science. It was found that prospective Teachers teaching physical and biological components of secondary science had equal tendency of inviting components of secondary science had equal tendency of inviting comments and seeking questions. Pupil participation was more in the classes of prospected Teachers teaching physical science components of secondary science as compared to the classes of Teachers teaching biological components. Students refer to Teacher mostly for the purpose of acquiring or confirming facts and principles.

Persichitte (2003) conducted a study on a continuing journey toward Technology Infusion within Teacher Preparation. The study describes the evaluation of pre-service Teacher technology courses at the University of Northern Colorado. The study highlighted on Technology integration, student teaching requirements, and student attitudes about technology. Revised curricula that included state and professional organization of technology standards, performance based assessments, instructional support for students and support for faculty.

Need and Significance of the Study:

India today needs competent, experienced and dedicated Teachers to provide quality education. It may not be an exaggeration to say that the present Teacher Education does not satisfactorily provide such a quality

education in the present day educational scenario. The present system imparts a training knowledge which cannot be applied in the regular class room practice.

Researchers did study Teacher effectiveness from the point of view of Teacher characteristics or Teacher behavior and its impact on the achievement of students. But similar studies have not been conducted in the problems of Students Teacher studying in Colleges of Education. There is a need for more comprehensive and sophisticated research and better dissemination of results so that these can be used for the improvement of Teacher Education programme within the frame work of the total educational system in the country.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out the problems of Student Teacher studying in Colleges of Education.
- ✓ To distinguish the different problems of Student Teacher studying in Colleges of Education with respect to Gender, Locality and Marital Status.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ The Student teachers studying in college of education are facing problems.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the problems of Student teachers studying in colleges of education with respect to gender, locality and Marital Status.

Method of Study:

In the present study normative survey method is adopted.

Sample of the Study:

The investigator proposed to take a random sample of 692 student teachers studying in various college of education in Salem District, Tamil Nadu.

Distribution of Samples:

Gender : Male – 193, Female – 499
 Locality : Rural – 469, Urban – 223
 Marital Status : Married – 44, Unmarried – 648

Tool Used:

Students’ teacher’s Problem Questionnaire was developed by Dr. Vijayal and 100 items for 10 components and each component consisted of 10 items.

Statistical Techniques Used:

- ✓ Computations of percentages are done for the problems of B.Ed. Student Teacher in Colleges of Education in various institutions.
- ✓ Computations of CR values are done for B.Ed. Student Teacher in Colleges of Education.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: Percentage Analysis of Problems of Student Teachers studying in College of Education with regards to Gender

S.No	Variable	Category	Low	%	Avg.	%	High	%	Total	%
1	Selection Procedure	Male	68	35.2	88	45.6	37	19.2	193	27.9
		Female	173	34.7	232	46.5	94	18.8	499	72.1
		Total	241	34.8	320	46.2	131	18.9	692	100.0
2	Micro Teaching	Male	60	31.1	104	53.9	29	15.0	193	27.9
		Female	161	32.3	254	50.9	84	16.8	499	72.1
		Total	221	31.9	358	51.7	113	16.3	692	100.0
3	Curriculum Transaction	Male	65	33.7	105	54.4	23	11.9	193	27.9
		Female	169	33.9	255	51.1	75	15.0	499	72.1
		Total	234	33.8	360	52.0	98	14.2	692	100.0
4	Lesson Plan	Male	9	4.7	11338	58.5	71	36.8	193	27.9
		Female	108	21.6	2	76.6	9	1.8	499	72.1
		Total	117	16.9	495	71.5	80	11.6	692	100.0
5	Student Teaching	Male	126	65.3	60	31.1	7	3.6	193	27.9
		Female	35	7.0	376	75.4	88	17.6	499	72.1
		Total	161	23.3	436	63.0	95	13.7	692	100.0
6	Educational Technology	Male	20	10.4	79	40.9	94	48.7	193	27.9
		Female	196	39.3	280	56.1	23	4.6	499	72.1
		Total	216	31.2	359	51.9	117	16.9	692	100.0
7	Techniques of Teaching	Male	105	54.4	80	41.5	8	4.1	193	27.9
		Female	31	6.2	417	83.6	51	10.2	499	72.1
		Total	136	19.7	497	71.8	59	8.5	692	100.0
8	Psychological Analysis	Male	67	34.7	97	50.3	29	15.0	193	27.9
		Female	92	18.4	360	72.1	47	9.4	499	72.1
		Total	159	23.0	457	66.0	76	11.0	692	100.0
9	Socio	Male	0	0.0	193	100.0	0	0.0	193	27.9

	economic status Total	Female	12	2.4	486	97.4	1	0.2	499	72.1
			12	1.7	679	98.1	1	0.1	692	100.0
10	Isolation Total	Male	17	8.8	135	69.9	41	21.2	193	27.9
		Female	93	18.6	361	72.3	45	9.0	499	72.1
		Total	110	15.9	496	71.7	86	12.4	692	100.0

Table 2: Percentage Analysis of Student Teachers studying in Colleges of Education with regards to Locality

S.No	Variable	Category	Low	%	Avg.	%	High	%	Total	%
1	Selection Procedure Total	Rural	164	35.0	208	44.3	97	20.7	469	67.8
		Urban	77	34.5	112	50.2	34	15.2	223	32.2
		Total	241	34.8	320	46.2	131	18.9	692	100.0
2	Micro Teaching Total	Rural	146	31.1	249	53.1	74	15.8	469	67.8
		Urban	75	33.6	109	48.9	39	17.5	223	32.2
		Total	221	31.9	358	51.7	113	16.3	692	100.0
3	Curriculum Transaction Total	Rural	167	35.6	236	50.3	66	14.1	469	67.8
		Urban	67	30.0	124	55.6	32	14.3	223	32.2
		Total	234	33.8	360	52.0	98	14.2	692	100.0
4	Lesson Plan Total	Rural	64	13.6	345	73.6	60	12.8	469	67.8
		Urban	53	23.8	150	67.3	20	9.0	223	32.2
		Total	117	16.9	495	71.5	80	11.6	692	100.0
5	Student Teaching Total	Rural	123	26.2	283	60.3	63	13.4	469	67.8
		Urban	38	17.0	153	68.6	32	14.3	223	32.2
		Total	161	23.3	436	63.0	95	13.7	692	100.0
6	Educational Technology Total	Rural	145	30.9	240	51.2	84	17.9	469	67.8
		Urban	71	31.8	119	53.4	33	14.8	223	32.2
		Total	216	31.2	359	51.9	117	16.9	692	100.0
7	Techniques of Teaching Total	Rural	105	22.4	324	69.1	40	8.5	469	67.8
		Urban	31	13.91	173	77.6	19	8.5	223	32.2
		Total	136	9.7	497	71.8	59	8.5	692	100.0
8	Psychological Analysis Total	Rural	110	23.5	315	67.2	44	9.4	469	67.8
		Urban	49	22.0	142	63.7	32	14.3	223	32.2
		Total	159	23.0	457	66.0	76	11.0	692	100.0
9	Socio Economic Status Total	Rural	9	1.9	460	98.1	0	0.0	469	67.8
		Urban	3	1.3	219	98.2	1	0.4	223	32.2
		Total	12	1.7	679	98.1	1	0.1	692	100.0
10	Isolation Total	Rural	76	16.2	341	72.7	52	11.1	469	67.8
		Urban	34	15.2	155	69.5	34	15.2	223	32.2
		Total	110	15.9	496	71.7	86	12.4	692	100.0

Differential Analysis – CR Test:

Table 3: CR Test for the Problems of Student Teachers in College of Education with respect to Gender

S.No	Category	Respondent	Number	Mean	SD	Cal. CR Value	Remarks at 0.05 level
1	Selection Procedure	Male	193	9.33	1.29	0.14	NS
		Female	499	9.32	1.31		
2	Micro Teaching	Male	193	11.62	1.55	0.51	NS
		Female	499	11.68	1.58		
3	Curriculum Transaction	Male	193	7.18	1.04	0.42	NS
		Female	499	7.22	1.08		
4	Lesson Plan	Male	193	11.05	2.31	16.12	S
		Female	499	8.13	1.61		
5	Student Teaching	Male	193	9.34	1.54	16.90	S
		Female	499	11.64	1.76		
6	Educational Technology	Male	193	12.11	1.97	19.12	S
		Female	499	9.13	1.41		
7	Techniques of Teaching	Male	193	10.60	2.10	12.83	S
		Female	499	12.71	1.47		
8	Psychological Analysis	Male	193	9.54	1.56	0.54	NS
		Female	499	9.61	1.21		
9	Socio Economic	Male	193	5.00	0.00	1.97	S

	Status	Female	499	4.98	0.20		
10	Isolation	Male	193	10.16	1.34	5.13	S
		Female	499	9.59	1.21		

Table 4: CR Test for the Problems of Student Teachers in College of Education with respect to marital status

S.No	Category	Respondent	Number	Mean	SD	Cal. CR Value	Remarks at 0.05 level
1	Selection Procedure	Single	648	9.30	1.29	1.39	NS
		Married	44	9.61	1.45		
2	Micro Teaching	Single	648	11.65	1.56	0.72	NS
		Married	44	11.84	1.68		
3	Curriculum transaction	Single	648	7.22	1.07	1.39	NS
		Married	44	7.00	1.02		
4	Lesson Plan	Single	648	8.98	2.29	1.86	S
		Married	44	8.50	1.60		
5	Student Teaching	Single	648	10.93	1.99	3.74	S
		Married	44	11.98	1.79		
6	Educational Technology	Single	648	10.00	2.10	2.02	S
		Married	44	9.48	1.62		
7	Techniques of Teaching	Single	648	12.09	1.94	2.36	S
		Married	44	12.64	1.46		
8	Psychological analysis	Single	648	9.59	1.32	0.01	NS
		Married	44	9.59	1.19		
9	Socio economic status	Single	648	4.98	0.13	0.87	NS
		Married	44	5.05	0.47		
10	Isolation	Single	648	9.74	1.28	0.95	NS
		Married	44	9.91	1.16		

Table 5: CR Test for the Problems of Student Teachers in College of Education with respect to Locality

S.No	Category	Respondent	Number	Mean	SD	Cal. CR Value	Remarks at 0.05 level
1	Selection Procedure	Rural	469	9.34	1.33	0.67	NS
		Urban	223	9.27	1.25		
2	Micro Teaching	Rural	469	11.69	1.56	0.68	NS
		Urban	223	11.61	1.59		
3	Curriculum transaction	Rural	469	7.19	1.08	0.74	NS
		Urban	223	7.25	1.04		
4	Lesson Plan	Rural	469	9.10	2.27	2.71	S
		Urban	223	8.62	2.17		
5	Student Teaching	Rural	469	10.91	2.03	1.56	NS
		Urban	223	11.16	1.90		
6	Educational Technology	Rural	469	10.08	2.11	2.13	S
		Urban	223	9.73	1.98		
7	Techniques of Teaching	Rural	469	12.00	2.03	2.56	S
		Urban	223	12.37	1.64		
8	Psychological analysis	Rural	469	9.56	1.28	0.96	NS
		Urban	223	9.66	1.39		
9	Socio economic status	Rural	469	4.98	0.14	1.14	NS
		Urban	223	5.00	0.23		
10	Isolation	Rural	469	9.73	1.25	0.53	NS
		Urban	223	9.78	1.32		

Findings of the Study:

The present study is proposed to find out the problems of Student Teachers studying in College of Education in Salem District, Tamilnadu.

- ✓ Findings on percentage analysis of Student Teachers in College of Education with respect to Sex and Locality.
- ✓ It is found that females were better than males in College of Education.
- ✓ The present study reveals that Rural Student Teachers have more problems than Urban Student Teachers in College of Education.

- ✓ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of nature of problems in selection procedure, microteaching, curriculum transaction and psychological analysis for the problems of Student Teachers in college of education with respect to gender.
- ✓ There is significant difference between the mean scores of nature of problems in lesson plan, student teaching, educational technology, techniques of teaching, socioeconomic status and Isolation for the problems of Student Teachers in college of education with respect to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of nature of problems in selection procedure, curriculum transaction, psychological analysis, socioeconomic status for the problems of Student Teachers in college of education with respect to marital status.
- ✓ There is significant difference between the mean scores of nature of problems in lesson plan, student teaching, educational technology and techniques of teaching for the problems of Student Teachers in college of education with respect to marital status.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of nature of problems in selection procedure, microteaching, curriculum transaction, student teaching, psychological analysis, socioeconomic status and isolation is not significant for the problems of Student Teachers in college of education with respect to locality.
- ✓ There is significant difference between the mean scores of nature of problems in lesson plan and educational technology for the problems of Student Teachers in college of education with respect to locality.

Conclusion:

The society is indebted to the Teachers who are in the noblest profession for shaping the destiny of the Nation, through the education of young minds and acknowledges teaching, as then noblest profession. The National Policy of Education and Programme of Action (1986) provided broad indication for the restructuring of Education including Teacher Education. It was realized that without improving the quality of Teacher Education the quality of school education cannot be improved. National Commission of Teachers (1983-1985) states that majority of our Colleges of Education and Training Institutes woefully inadequate and in the content of the changing needs of India today. Recommendations of the Kothari Commission pointed out that the “Essence of a programme of Teacher Education is ‘quality’ and in its absence, Teacher Education becomes not only a financial waste but source of overall deterioration in educational standards. The mushroom growth of college of Education Institutes creates no quality assurance in Teacher Education Programme. Hence, modification and improvement in teaching methodology and technique should be introduced through new practices and innovations. The quality should be maintained using new practices and innovations like microteaching, simulated social skill training, interaction analysis technique and action research for student teaching. Hence the enhancement of programmes of Teacher Education should be an urgent need for implementation in our country.

References:

1. Anjسونi, 2003. Theory and Principles of Education.
2. Barry, mirroring practice Reflections of teacher educator Education Canada – 1997.
3. Biswas, A., J.C. Aggrawal. Comparative Education, 2004.
4. Dalaganjan Nask, 1994. Teaching skills through microteaching.
5. Jonatha, W. 1992. Border land contrasts in a microteaching laboratory- American Educational Studies.
6. Kothari Education Commission (1966). Government of India Document, New Delhi, Ministry of Education.
7. Leleu marviel – script creation for the design of lesson plans – 2002 Journal of Technology and Teacher Education.
8. Mathew, V.S. 2004. Studies in Indian Education.
9. Miller, John. W. A comparison of alternatively and traditionally prepared teachers. Journal of Teacher Education 1999.
10. Mohanty, J., 1992. Current issues in Education.
11. Dr. S. Packiam, 1986. Secondary Education in Tamilnadu, A growth study.
12. Persichitte, 2003. A continuing journey toward Technology Infusion with in Teacher preparation. Teach. Trends V.47
13. Reddy R.S., 1998. Principles and practices of Teacher Education.
14. Dr. M.S. Sachdeva, 1993. A new approach Teacher and Education. In Indian Society.
15. Dr. Sharma, 1992. Principles of Education.
16. Dr. Singh, R.P., 2004. Professional education in ancient and medieval India.
17. Stanik, Jospeh, T. Bhaghadd in classical era. 2004. Journal annucement.